

Structure and reactivity of binary Au₁₂Pt cluster

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Abstract : An all-electron scalar relativistic calculation on the geometrical structure and reactivity of Au₁₂Pt cluster has been performed by using density functional theory with the generalized gradient approximation at PW91 level. The lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂Pt cluster is generated by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of the Au₁₃ cluster at the highest coordinated site. Compared with pure Au₁₃ cluster, the Au₁₂Pt cluster is less stable and more reactive. The CO molecule and O₂ molecule prefer to be adsorbed onto the Pt atom above the planes of the lowest energy geometries for Au₁₂PtCO and Au₁₂PtO₂ clusters. The impurity Pt is favorable to the adsorptions and also promotes the reactivity enhancement of CO molecule and O₂ molecule.

Keywords : Binary Au₁₂Pt cluster, geometrical structure, chemical reactivity toward CO and O₂.

Introduction

Gold clusters have been found to be active catalysts for many reactions of industrial and environmental interest^{1,2}. As one of the key factors to understand the catalytic mechanism of reducing air pollution, the adsorption behaviors of gold clusters toward some small molecules have been studied experimentally and theoretically³⁻⁵. It is found that the adsorption behavior of these molecules on gold clusters strongly depends on the charge states and the size of gold clusters.

Apart from the pure gold clusters, in order to increase the number of variables for the purpose of material design and control, some doped gold clusters composed of two or more elements have also been studied extensively in the recent years⁶⁻⁹. The properties of doped gold clusters depend not only on the cluster size and geometry, but also on the cluster composition. Heterogeneous clusters are expected to show an extremely rich variety of catalytic behaviors as a function of the composition and chemical order. The exploration of the structure of these heterogeneous gold clusters may help to understand the catalytic activity of these catalysts and the interaction of the doped metal with the metal cluster. Among all these heterogeneous gold clusters, the platinum doped gold clusters attract strong attention for their

potential application in catalysis¹⁰⁻¹³. In fact, the gold-platinum bimetallic clusters have been investigated experimentally for their role in CO adsorption and oxidation¹¹, NO adsorption and reduction¹², CH₃OH oxidation¹³. It is established that these bimetallic systems are better catalysts than pure metal clusters¹⁴. This increase in catalytic activity is determined by controllable factors such as composition, temperature and the method of preparation. Meanwhile, some theoretical studies on gold-platinum bimetallic clusters also can be found¹⁵⁻¹⁹. The bimetallic clusters AuPt and Au₆Pt have been studied for their structure and reactivity within density functional theory¹⁵. The Au-Pt bond in AuPt cluster is stronger than the Au-Au bond in Au₂ cluster and weaker than the Pt-Pt bond in Pt₂ cluster. The Pt atom is the reactive center in both AuPt and AuPt⁺ clusters. The most stable structure of Au₆Pt cluster is a quasi-planar hexagonal frame with Pt lying at the hexagonal center. The O₂ prefers to be adsorbed on Au and the CO prefers to be adsorbed on Pt. The adsorption of AuPt cluster toward O₂ and CO is stronger than the corresponding adsorption on Au₆Pt cluster. Guo *et al.* have studied the geometries of the lowest-lying isomers of Au_nPt₂ (*n* = 1-4) clusters¹⁶. It is suggested that the gold-platinum interaction may improve the stability of clusters. The larger of the Au_n cluster, the

smaller of the distortions by substitution of the two Pt atoms. Yuan *et al.* report the ground state geometric and electronic structures of gold clusters doped with platinum group atoms Au_nM ($n = 1-7$, $M = Ni, Pd, Pt$) by employing the Amsterdam density-functional (ADF) program package¹⁷. Due to the strong relativistic effects and unique properties of dopant delocalized *s*-electrons in Pt-doped gold clusters, the geometric and electronic properties of doped gold clusters are changed obviously. The chemical reactivity between these doped gold clusters and gas molecules is also improved.

Given an overview of these studies, cluster size up to seven is far from enough, further studies on some larger gold-platinum bimetallic clusters are necessary. Furthermore, among all these studies, few are available to consider the influence of scalar relativistic effect^{16,17}. Gold being a heavy element, the scalar relativistic effect of outer shell electrons is obvious and can not be neglected²⁰⁻²⁶. Previous studies^{24,25} indicate that the reason for the preference of planar structures by gold clusters up to large size may be attributed to the scalar relativistic effects that cause the shrinking of the size of *s* orbitals, and thus enhance the *s-d* hybridization. This phenomenon is most strikingly evident in gold cluster and called "gold maximum"²⁶. So for coinage metal cluster in general, and gold cluster in particular, it is essential to include scalar relativistic effect in the study of gold clusters or gold-based mixed clusters. In this paper, we shall perform an all-electron scalar relativistic (AER) calculation on $Au_{12}Pt$ cluster under the framework of density functional theory with the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) at PW91 level in order to investigate the influence of impurity Pt on the geometrical structure and reactivity by complete comparison with corresponding Au_{13} cluster. It is hoped that this work would be useful to understand the influence of material structure on its properties and could offer relevant information for further experimental and theoretical studies.

Computational method and cluster model :

All calculations are based on spin-polarized DFT in the DMOL 3 program package^{27,28}. A double-numerical basis set, together with *d*-polarization functions (DNP), is chosen to describe the electronic wave functions. Within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA), the Perdew-Wang 91 exchange-correlation (XC) functional

(PW91)²⁹, combined with the DFT-basis all-electron treatment and scalar or spin-orbit all-electron relativistic pseudopotentials³⁰ is used in the calculations. These potentials do not replace core electrons; instead they supplement the core potentials with approximate relativistic effects. Such effects are important for heavier elements, and are certainly required starting with the second row of transition metals. Using these potentials may yield the most accurate results, though at the highest cost^{27,28}.

Self-consistent field calculations are done with a convergence criterion of 10^{-6} Ha on the total energy. The density mixing criteria for charge and spin are 0.02 and 0.05, respectively. In the geometry optimization, the convergence thresholds are set to be 0.002 Ha/Å for the forces, 0.005 Å for the displacement, and 10^{-5} Ha for the energy change. During the structure relaxation, various possible spin multiplicities will be considered. If the total energy decreases with increasing of the spin multiplicity, the high spin state will be considered until the energy minimum with respect to the spin multiplicity is reached. In addition, the stability of the optimized geometry is confirmed without any imaginary frequency by computing harmonic vibrational frequencies at the same level of theory.

The choice of distinct initial geometries is important to the reliability of obtained lowest energy structures. In this work, we get the initial structures by the following way. First, considering previous studies on the configurations of pure gold clusters^{24,31-34}, we optimize the structures of pure Au_{12} and Au_{13} clusters by using the same method and same parameters. On the basis of the optimized equilibrium geometries of pure Au_{12} and Au_{13} clusters, we obtain the initial structures of $Au_{12}Pt$ cluster by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of the Au_{13} cluster at every nonequivalent site or by adding Pt atom directly on each possible nonequivalent site of Au_{12} cluster. All these initial structures are fully optimized by relaxing the atomic positions until the force acting on each atom vanishes (typically $|F_i| \leq 0.002$ Ha/Å) and by minimizing the total energy.

In order to check the intrinsic quality of the scheme for the description of $Au_{12}Pt$ cluster, we first consider Au_2 , Pt_2 , $AuPt$ and $AuPtCO$ clusters for which experimental or theoretical data are available for comparison. The calculated bond-lengths, binding energies and verti-

cal ionization potentials for Au₂ and Pt₂ clusters in our work are 2.487 Å, 2.43 eV, 9.38 eV and 2.355 Å, 3.39 eV, 8.74 eV, respectively. These results are in good agreement with the experimental values of 2.473 Å, 2.31 ± 0.005 eV, 9.40 eV for Au₂ cluster³⁵ and 2.333 Å, 3.14 ± 0.02 eV, 8.68 ± 0.02 eV for Pt₂ cluster^{36,37}. Meanwhile, the calculated bond-length of 2.458 Å, binding energy of 2.65 eV and doublet multiplicity for AuPt cluster in our work are all consistent with previous DFT results of 2.560 Å, 2.63 eV and doublet multiplicity in Guo *et al.*¹⁶. Furthermore, for AuPtCO cluster, the C–O bond-length of 1.160 Å and Pt–C bond-length of 1.818 Å in our work are consistent well with the 1.166 Å and 1.831 Å of previous work¹⁵. Therefore, we are confident that the adopted computational method is reliable and accurate enough for the study of Au₁₂Pt cluster.

Results and discussion

Structure and stability :

Geometrical structures :

First, we optimize the pure Au₁₂ and Au₁₃ clusters. These lowest energy planar structures displayed in Fig. 1(a) and (b) are in good agreement with previous works^{24,31–34}. Then, based on these optimized lowest en-

ergy structures of Au₁₂ and Au₁₃ clusters, we perform an extensive lowest energy structures search for small gold clusters doped with one platinum atom according to the way described in Section Computational method and cluster model. The lowest energy structure and some typical isomers are also plotted in Fig. 1 according to the sequence of energies from low to high. Meanwhile, the Au–Au and Au–Pt bond-lengths, symmetry, electronic state and energy difference between lowest energy structure and its isomer are also indicated in this figure.

The lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂Pt cluster shown in Fig. 1(c) is a triangular structure constructed by fourteen small triangles. The corresponding symmetry and electronic state are C_{2v} and ¹B₂, respectively. It may be generated by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of the Au₁₃ cluster at the highest coordinated site. Other optimized structures obtained by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of Au₁₃ cluster at the doubly, triply and quadruply coordinated site or bonding Pt atom directly on possible nonequivalent site of Au₁₂ cluster are low-lying geometric isomers with higher energy. Compared with corresponding pure Au₁₃ or Au₁₂ cluster, the lowest energy geometry and most isomers of Au₁₂Pt cluster are distorted slightly and still keep the planar structures. This

Fig. 1. Optimized geometries for pure Au₁₂, Au₁₃ clusters and Au₁₂Pt cluster. The Au–Au, Au–Pt bond-lengths in angstrom, symmetry, electronic state and energy difference between lowest energy structure and its isomer are shown next to each cluster.

situation also can be seen in some previous works^{15,16} and believed to be the reflection of strong scalar relativistic effects in small gold clusters^{24,25}. Only the structure generated by bonding one Pt atom above the plane of Au₁₂ cluster, the plane is bent and up-swelled obviously after optimization. It is interesting that all the optimized geometries generated by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of Au₁₃ cluster are more stable than those generated by bonding Pt atom directly on possible nonequivalent site of Au₁₂ cluster. The relatively favorable generation way for Au₁₂Pt cluster seems to be the substitution Pt atom for one gold atom of Au₁₃ cluster. In all these optimized structures of Au₁₂Pt cluster, the Au-Pt bond-lengths and most Au-Au bond-lengths are shorter than the corresponding Au-Au bond-lengths in pure Au₁₃ cluster, only a few Au-Au bond-lengths far from Pt atom are elongated, indicating that the Au-Pt bonds and most Au-Au bonds are strengthened, and only a few Au-Au bonds far from Pt atom are weakened after doping platinum atom.

Chemical stabilities :

To gain insight into the chemical stability of pure Au₁₃ cluster and Au₁₂Pt cluster, the vertical ionization potentials (VIP) and vertical electron affinity (VEA) are calculated and listed in Table 1. Where we define :

$$\text{VIP} = E(\text{Au}_{13})^+ - E(\text{Au}_{13})$$

$$\text{VIP} = E(\text{Au}_{12}\text{Pt})^+ - E(\text{Au}_{12}\text{Pt})$$

$$\text{VEA} = E(\text{Au}_{13}) - E(\text{Au}_{13})^-$$

$$\text{VEA} = E(\text{Au}_{12}\text{Pt}) - E(\text{Au}_{12}\text{Pt})^-$$

At first glance of the calculation results of VIP and VEA listed in Table 1, the VIP of Au₁₂Pt cluster is smaller than that of corresponding pure Au₁₃ cluster, and the VEA of Au₁₂Pt cluster is larger than that of corresponding Au₁₃ cluster. That is to say, for neutral Au₁₂Pt cluster, when one electron is ionized or added, less energy is required or much energy is released compared with the same process in pure Au₁₃ cluster. The productions of the corresponding ion and anion are more easily to be accomplished. It is suggested that the Au₁₂Pt cluster gen-

erated by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of Au₁₃ cluster at the highest coordinated site is less stable and more reactive than the corresponding Au₁₃ cluster chemically.

In addition to above parameters, the maximum hardness principle (MHP) also can be used to characterize the chemical stability of a system^{38,39}. In density functional theory, the chemical hardness (η) of an electronic system is defined as the second derivative of energy (E) with respect to the number of electrons (N) at constant external potential. By using the finite difference approximation and the Koopmans' theorem, chemical hardness η can be approximated as :

$$\eta = \frac{\text{VIP} - \text{VEP}}{2}$$

where the VIP and VEA are vertical ionization potential and vertical electron affinity of the chemical system^{31,40-43}.

Based on this finite difference approximation and by combining use the calculation results of VIP and VEA, the chemical hardness for the lowest energy structures of pure Au₁₃ and Au₁₂Pt clusters are calculated and listed in Table 1. It is easy to be found that the value of chemical hardness for Au₁₂Pt cluster is obviously smaller than that for corresponding pure Au₁₃ cluster. According to the maximum hardness principle (MHP)^{44,45}, it proves again that the Au₁₂Pt cluster with small chemical hardness is less stable and more reactive chemically than the corresponding pure Au₁₃ cluster with larger chemical hardness.

In order to understand the nature of chemical bonding in these systems, we have plotted the spatial orientation of some frontier orbitals for pure Au₁₃ cluster and Au₁₂Pt cluster in Fig. 2 comparatively. At first sight, the distribution of electron cloud in the frontier orbitals of pure Au₁₃ cluster is well-mixed and uniform relatively. The delocalization is obviously with a contribution from almost all atoms in the cluster. The strong *spd* orbital hybridization in gold atom or between gold atoms is strong relatively. This picture may be explained in terms of the strong scalar relativistic effect in small gold cluster²⁴⁻²⁶. The strong scalar relativistic effect caused by the high speed motion of out shell electrons and the spin-orbit

Table 1. Calculated energy data for Au₁₂Pt cluster and corresponding pure Au₁₃ cluster

Cluster	VIP (eV)	VEA (eV)	η (eV)
Au ₁₃	6.86	3.59	1.64
Au ₁₂ Pt	6.61	3.93	1.34

Fig. 2. Spatial orientations of some frontier orbitals for pure Au₁₃ cluster and Au₁₂Pt cluster.

coupling leads to the shrinking of the size of the *s* orbitals, lowers the corresponding energy level and enhances the shielding effect of inner electrons. Thus, promotes the outward expanding of the *d*, *f* orbitals and makes the *s*, *d* electrons closer. The enhancement of *s-d* hybridization is very obvious and the frontier orbitals become dispersive. After doping Pt atom, for the frontier orbitals of Au₁₂Pt cluster, more electron cloud is localized near the Pt atom. The degree of delocalization of these frontier orbitals is reduced to some extent. It is inferred that the chemical reactivity may be improved and the Pt atom is the most possible reactive center.

Adsorption :

To further check the chemical reactivity of Au₁₂Pt cluster toward small molecules, the adsorptions of single CO and O₂ onto Au₁₂Pt are explored. The fully optimized geometries of Au₁₃CO, Au₁₃O₂, Au₁₂PtCO and Au₁₂PtO₂ clusters including some low-lying geometric isomers with higher energy and single CO, O₂ molecules are depicted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively.

Adsorption toward CO :

For Au₁₃CO cluster, the lowest energy geometry belongs to the structure described in Fig. 3(b). The carbon monoxide molecule prefers to occupy the on-top and single fold coordination site. The small gold cluster would like to bond with carbon. The geometry still keeps the planar structure like the pure Au₁₃ cluster and the Au, C and O atoms locate in the same line. The C-O bond-length is

elongated from the 1.140 Å in single CO molecule to the 1.151 Å in Au₁₃CO cluster. For Au₁₂PtCO cluster, the lowest energy geometry is the structure displayed in Fig. 3(c). It is generated by bonding CO molecule with Pt atom above the plane of Au₁₂Pt cluster. After optimization, the plane is bent and up-swelled, and the distortion of the structure is very obvious. The Pt-C bond-length is significantly shorter and C-O bond-length is obviously longer than the corresponding bond-length in Au₁₃CO cluster. The Au-C bond-lengths in the optimized low lying isomers generated by bonding CO molecule with Au atom in the same plane of Au₁₂Pt cluster are longer than the Au-C bond-lengths in Au₁₃CO cluster and the Pt-C bond-length in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster. The C-O bond-lengths in these isomers are close to the C-O bond-length in Au₁₃CO cluster and shorter than the C-O bond-length in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster. It is inferred that in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster, the adsorption toward CO molecule is stronger and the reactivity enhancement of CO molecule is more significant than the adsorption in the low lying isomers relatively. The Pt atom might be the reactive center of adsorption toward CO molecule.

From the adsorption energies listed in Table 2, we can see that the largest adsorption energy belongs to the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster depicted in

(e) $C_s, {}^1A_g, \Delta E = 0.88 \text{ eV}$ (f) $C_{2v}, {}^1A_2, \Delta E = 0.90 \text{ eV}$ (g) $C_{2v}, {}^1A_2, \Delta E = 1.28 \text{ eV}$ (h) $C_s, {}^1A_g, \Delta E = 1.31 \text{ eV}$

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Fig. 3. Optimized geometries for single CO molecule, Au_{13}CO and $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtCO}$ clusters. The Au-C and C-O bond-lengths in angstrom, symmetry, electronic state and energy difference between lowest energy geometry and isomer are shown next to each cluster.

Fig. 4. Optimized geometries for single O_2 molecule, Au_{13}O_2 and $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ clusters. The Au-O and O-O bond-lengths in angstrom, symmetry, electronic state and energy difference between lowest energy geometry and isomer are shown next to each cluster.

Table 2. Calculated adsorption energy, highest vibrational frequencies of Au–C mode and C–O mode, effective charge for Au₁₃CO cluster, Au₁₂PtCO cluster and single CO molecule

Figure	Cluster	E_{ad} (eV)	$\nu_{Au(Pt)-C}$ (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{C-O} (cm ⁻¹)	Effective charge		
					Au ₁₂ Pt (Au ₁₃)	C	O
3(a)	CO			2115.0		0.105	-0.105
3(b)	Au ₁₃ CO	1.78	467.6	2073.1	-0.154	0.285	-0.131
3(c)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	2.11	514.1	2043.2	-0.182	0.331	-0.109
3(d)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	1.71	456.3	2073.8	-0.146	0.276	-0.130
3(e)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	1.70	444.0	2076.1	-0.142	0.274	-0.132
3(f)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	1.61	447.4	2085.0	-0.142	0.276	-0.134
3(g)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	1.59	437.2	2068.3	-0.129	0.259	-0.130
3(h)	Au ₁₂ PtCO	1.41	424.5	2065.0	-0.128	0.256	-0.128

Fig. 3(c). Meanwhile, the highest vibrational frequency of Pt–C mode and the highest vibrational frequency of C–O mode for the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster are obviously higher and lower than the corresponding frequencies for the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₃CO cluster and low lying isomers of Au₁₂PtCO cluster, respectively. It is suggested that the Pt–C interaction and the C–O interaction in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster is stronger and weaker than the corresponding interactions in Au₁₃CO cluster and low lying isomers of Au₁₂PtCO cluster. In addition, the interaction between small Au₁₂Pt cluster and carbon monoxide molecule also can be reflected through charge transfer. We perform a Mulliken charge analysis for Au₁₂PtCO cluster and list the effective charges on Au₁₂Pt, C and O in Table 2. The value of charge transfer suggests a mechanism to favor of electron donation, that is, charge transfer from CO molecule to Au₁₂Pt cluster, the Au₁₂Pt cluster behaves as a charge acceptor. On the basis of cluster and surface studies^{44,45}, this can be explained in terms of the electron donation from the $p\pi$ orbital of CO to the $d\sigma + sp$ hybridized orbital of Au₁₂Pt and the electron back donation from the occupied $d\pi$ orbital of Au₁₂Pt to the unoccupied $p\pi$ orbital of CO molecule, which results the better overlap of these orbitals and the enhancement of platinum-carbon bond or gold-carbon bond. Greater charge transfer often leads to larger adsorption energy. This can be confirmed by Au₁₂PtCO cluster. From Table 2, we can easily find that the largest charge transfer takes place in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster with the shortest Pt–C bond-length and largest adsorption energy. The variation of charge transfers is consistent well with the variation of adsorption energies.

Meanwhile, we can also find that the carbon loses electrons, and the oxygen gains some amount of electrons. Namely, the electrons transfer not only from carbon to Au₁₂Pt but also from carbon to oxygen. The larger of the charge transfer, which results in a stronger hybridization with the host, the stronger of the specified bonding. Obviously, the charge transfer from C to O in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster described in Fig. 3(c) is smaller than those in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₃CO cluster and low lying isomers of Au₁₂PtCO clusters. The C–O bond in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster described in Fig. 3(c) is weaker than those in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₃CO cluster and other isomers of Au₁₂PtCO clusters, appearing as the longest C–O bond-length, which can be observed clearly in Fig. 3(c). These pictures of adsorption energies, frequencies and charge transfer prove again that the strongest adsorption and the greatest reactivity enhancement of CO molecule might exist in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂PtCO cluster displayed in Fig. 3(c).

Adsorption toward O₂ :

With regard to the O₂ molecule adsorption onto Au₁₃ and Au₁₂Pt clusters, the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₃O₂ cluster belongs to the structure described in Fig. 4(b). The O₂ molecule prefers to occupy the on-top and single fold coordination site. The O–O bond-length is elongated from the 1.225 Å in single O₂ molecule to the 1.280 Å in Au₁₃O₂ cluster. For Au₁₂PtO₂ cluster, the lowest energy geometry is the structure displayed in Fig. 4(c). It is generated by bonding O₂ molecule with Pt atom above the plane of Au₁₂Pt cluster. Other optimized geometries generated by bonding O₂ molecule with Au atom in the same plane of Au₁₂Pt cluster are low-lying isomers with

higher energy. For the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster, the Au_{12}Pt structure is slightly bent after optimization, and the Pt-O-O bond angle and Au-O-O bond angles are slightly larger than the Au-O-O bond angle in Au_{13}O_2 cluster. The Pt-O bond-lengths and the O-O bond-lengths are shorter and longer than the corresponding bond-lengths in Au_{13}O_2 cluster. It is indicated that the doped impurity Pt might promote the adsorption and reactivity enhancement toward O_2 molecule.

From the adsorption energies and the highest vibrational frequencies listed in Table 3, we can see that the adsorption energies of all optimized $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ clusters

charge acceptor. The largest charge transfer exists in the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster with the largest adsorption energy. The variation of charge transfers is consistent well with the variation of adsorption energies. Due to the charges of two oxygen atom with the same electrical sign, they will repel each other. The anti-bonding between two oxygen atoms can be observed and may also destabilize the orbital of O_2 molecule, appearing as the lengthening of O-O bond. The larger charge transfer often corresponds to the stronger anti-bonding effect. This can be proved by the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster with the largest charge transfer and longest O-O bond-length.

Table 3. Calculated adsorption energy, highest vibrational frequencies of Au-O mode and O-O mode, effective charge for Au_{13}O_2 cluster, $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster and single O_2 molecule

Figure	Cluster	E_{ad} (eV)	$\nu_{\text{Au(Pt)-C}}$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (cm^{-1})	Effective charge		
					Au_{12}Pt (Au_{13})	O	O
4(a)	O_2			1549.1		0.000	0.000
4(b)	Au_{13}O_2	0.67	383.6	1211.0	0.221	-0.151	-0.070
4(c)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	1.02	570.5	1003.0	0.396	-0.194	-0.202
4(d)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	0.91	486.3	1083.5	0.352	-0.173	-0.179
4(e)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	0.89	464.0	1126.0	0.307	-0.167	-0.140
4(f)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	0.81	450.1	1144.0	0.291	-0.152	-0.139
4(g)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	0.80	439.5	1169.5	0.271	-0.149	-0.122
4(h)	$\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$	0.72	418.0	1195.0	0.242	-0.133	-0.109

are larger than the adsorption energy of the lowest energy Au_{13}O_2 cluster, the largest adsorption energy belongs to the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster depicted in Fig. 4(c) in which the highest vibrational frequencies of Pt-O mode and O-O mode are higher and lower than the corresponding frequencies for the lowest energy geometry of Au_{13}O_2 cluster and other optimized geometries of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ clusters, respectively. It is suggested that the Pt-O interaction in the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster is stronger than the corresponding Au-O interaction in Au_{13}O_2 cluster and other optimized geometries of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ clusters, and the O-O interaction is weaker than the O-O interaction in Au_{13}O_2 cluster and other optimized geometries of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ clusters. This situation is consistent well with the shortest Au-O bond-length and longest O-O bond-length which can be observed clearly in the lowest energy geometry of $\text{Au}_{12}\text{PtO}_2$ cluster depicted in Fig.4(c). Meanwhile, from Table 3, we can also see that the charge transfer from Au_{12}Pt to O_2 molecule, the O_2 molecule behaves as a

Conclusions :

An all-electron scalar relativistic calculation on the geometrical structure and reactivity of Au_{12}Pt cluster has been performed by using density functional theory with the generalized gradient approximation at PW91 level. The main conclusions are summarized as follows :

(i) The lowest energy geometry of Au_{12}Pt cluster may be generated by substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of the Au_{13} cluster at the highest coordinated site. The Au-Pt bonds and most Au-Au bonds are stronger and only a few Au-Au bonds far from Pt atom are weaker than the corresponding Au-Au bond in Au_{13} cluster.

(ii) By substituting Pt atom for one gold atom of the Au_{13} cluster, the Au_{12}Pt cluster is less stable than the corresponding Au_{13} cluster chemically. The chemical reactivity can be improved and the Pt atom may be the possible reactive center.

(iii) The strongest adsorption and the greatest reactivity enhancement of CO molecule and O_2 molecule take

place in the case that the CO molecule and O₂ molecule are adsorbed onto Pt atom in the lowest energy geometry of Au₁₂Pt cluster. The impurity Pt is favorable to the adsorption toward CO and O₂, and also promotes the reactivity enhancement of CO molecule and O₂ molecule.

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References

- M. Okumura, S. Nakamura, S. Tsubota, T. Nakamura, M. Azuma and M. Haruta, *Catal. Lett.*, 1998, **51**, 53.
- M. Haruta, *Chem. Rec.*, 2003, **3**, 75.
- S. Phala, G. Klatt and E. V. Steen, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2004, **395**, 33.
- M. Okumura, Y. Kitagawa, M. Haruta and K. Yamaguchi, *Appl. Catal. (A)*, 2005, **291**, 37.
- M. Okumura, Y. Kitagawa, H. Yabushita, T. Saito and T. Kawakami, *Catal. Today*, 2009, **143**, 282.
- X. Li, B. Kiran, L. F. Cui and L. S. Wang, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2005, **95**, 253401.
- S. F. Li, X. L. Xue, Y. Jia, G. F. Zhao, M. F. Zhang and X. G. Gong, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2006, **73**, 165401.
- L. M. Wang, J. Bai, A. Lechtken, W. Huang, D. Schooss, M. M. Kappes, X. C. Zeng and L. S. Wang, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2009, **79**, 033413.
- X. J. Li and K. H. Su, *Theor. Chem. Acc.*, 2009, **124**, 345.
- K. Koszinowski, D. Schroder and H. Schwarz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 3676.
- B. D. Chandler, A. B. Schobel and L. H. Pignolet, *J. Catal.*, 2000, **193**, 186.
- C. Mihut, C. Descorne, D. Duprez and M. D. Amiridis, *J. Catal.*, 2002, **212**, 125.
- J. Luo, M. M. Maye, N. N. Kariuki, L. Wang, P. Njoki, Y. Lin, M. Schadt, H. R. Naslund and C. J. Zhong, *Catal. Today*, 2005, **99**, 291.
- E. Bus and J. A. van Bokhoven, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2007, **111**, 9761.
- W. Q. Tian, M. F. Ge, F. L. Gu, T. Yamada and Y. Aoki, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2006, **110**, 6285.
- J. J. Guo, J. X. Yang and D. Dong, *J. Mol. Struct. Theochem.*, 2006, **764**, 117.
- D. W. Yuan, Y. Wang and Z. Zeng, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2005, **122**, 114310.
- O. Ü. Aktürk and M. Tomak, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2009, **80**, 085417.
- A. M. Joshi, M. H. Tucker, W. N. Delgass and K. T. Thomson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **125**, 194707.
- S. N. Datta, C. S. Ewig and J. R. VanWazer, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1978, **57**, 83.
- Y. S. Lee, W. C. Ermler and K. S. Pitzer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1997, **67**, 5861.
- P. K. Jain, *Struct. Chem.*, 2005, **16**, 421.
- S. Gilb, P. Weis, F. Furche, P. Ahlrichs and M. Kappes, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2002, **116**, 4094.
- E. M. Fernandez, J. M. Soler, L. L. Garzon and C. Balbas, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2004, **70**, 165403.
- R. Wesendrup, T. Hunt and P. Schwerdtfeger, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2000, **112**, 9356.
- J. Autschbach, S. Siekierski, M. Seth, P. Schwerdtfeger and W. H. E. Schwarz, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2002, **23**, 804.
- B. Delley, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1990, **92**, 508.
- B. Delley, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2000, **113**, 7756.
- J. P. Perdew and Y. Wang, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1992, **45**, 13244.
- B. Delley, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2002, **66**, 155125.
- A. Deka and R. C. Deka, *J. Mole. Struct. (Theochem.)*, 2008, **870**, 83.
- H. P. Mao, H. Y. Wang, Y. Ni and G. L. Xu, *Acta Physica Sinica*, 2004, **53**, 1766.
- H. Myoung, M. Ge, B. R. Sahu, P. Tarakeswar and K. S. Kim, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2003, **107**, 9994.
- H. Hakkinen and U. Landman, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 2000, **62**, 2287.
- B. Simard and P. A. Hackett, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1990, **142**, 310.
- S. Taylor, G. W. Lemire, Y. M. Hamrick, Z. Fu and M. D. Morse, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1988, **89**, 5517.
- B. A. Marc and M. D. Morse, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2002, **116**, 1313.
- R. G. Parr and P. K. Chattaraj, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 1854.
- R. G. Pearsom, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1987, **64**, 561.
- K. Fukui, *Science*, 1982, **218**, 747.
- M. Boyukata and Z. B. Guvenc, *J. Alloys. Compounds*, 2011, **509**, 4214.
- L. Guo, *J. Alloys. Compounds*, 2010, **498**, 121.
- J. G. He, K. G. Wu, C. P. Liu and R. G. Sa, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2009, **483**, 30.
- A. Poater, M. Duran, P. Jaque, A. Toro-Labbe and M. Sola, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2006, **110**, 6526.
- J. A. Rodriguez and C. T. Campbell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 2161.

